

Seismic characterization analyses of the Bulgarian Black Sea shelf for assessment of reservoir properties

Gergana Meracheva, Efrosima Zaneva-Dobranova, Nikolay Hristov

Faculty of Geology and Exploration, University of Mining and Geology, 1700 Sofia, Bulgaria;
e-mails: g.meracheva@gmail.com; e.zaneva@gmail.com; nk.hristov@gmail.com

(Received: 22 August 2022; accepted in revised form: 03 November 2022)

Abstract. In the Bulgarian Black Sea shelf, several gas fields have been discovered in Maastrichtian–Paleocene sediments to date. In this study, amplitude versus offset analysis (AVO) was carried out, and the extended elastic impedance (EEI) was also used, to predict fluid and lithology properties. Thus, in these special cases, AVO (or reflection angle) can significantly de-risk the existing Paleocene prospects and allow to focus on the Miocene–Oligocene successions, where some prospects have also been identified. By examining the variations in angle amplitude (or offset), it is possible to unravel lithology and fluid effects on the top of a reservoir. Seismic modeling is used to determine what type of seismic response, in terms of AVO, to expect at the depth of interest in the study area. There are five classes or types of AVO responses, and in the study area classes 1 and 2 were defined in the Miocene–Oligocene prospects. Brine-filled reservoirs and conglomerates exhibit class 1 AVO response, whereas gas-filled reservoirs show class 2 AVO responses. EEI has the ability to give estimates for elastic parameters, such as V_p/V_s ratio, bulk modulus, shear modulus, Poisson's ratio and other parameters. In the current study, simultaneous inversion testing was done and, analyzing all the wells together, Poisson's ratio is the most promising fluid and lithology indicator, showing good separation between water and gas responses, although there is some overlap. Projection of EEI at an angle of 38° through brine points gives a useful separation of brine, 10% gas and 90% gas reservoirs. However, the amplitude of the resulting projection is still low, which may make it difficult to resolve fluid variation once seismic noise has been added.

Meracheva, G., Zaneva-Dobranova, E., Hristov, N. 2022. Seismic characterization analyses of Bulgarian Black Sea shelf for assessment of reservoir properties. *Geologica Balcanica* 51 (3), 29–42.

Keywords: reservoir characterization, seismic attributes, Bulgarian Black Sea shelf.

INTRODUCTION

In the northern part of the Bulgarian Black Sea shelf, several gas fields, which are associated with structural (fault) trap types and whose reservoirs are composed of Maastrichtian–Paleocene bioclastic successions, have been established and are being exploited. The first discovery (in 1994) was the Galata gas field. After 2009, the Kaliakra and Kavarna fields were also discovered, with geological and reservoir characteristics similar to those of

the Galata field. The Bliznatsi fault, together with the Kaliakra fault zone and local faults, played an important role in the formation of the traps. Large-scale 2D and 3D seismic studies were used to clarify the geological structure of the area, the traps and the petrophysical characteristics of the Maastrichtian–Paleocene sedimentary successions, the interpretation of which helped make the discoveries.

The analysis of studies elsewhere (*e.g.*, the oil fields in the Gulf of Mexico, West Africa, and the United Arab Emirates) shows that specific param-

eters, such as the amplitude versus offset (AVO), the extended elastic impedance (EEI) and their combination, are significant for determining the rock varieties with different petrophysical and reservoir properties and achieving better reservoir assessment, thus reducing the risk of drilling dry wells (see Whitcombe *et al.*, 2002; Shahri, 2013).

This study aims to examine several hypotheses: 1) Can the proposed research approach, by using AVO and EEI analyses and their combination (Hicks and Francis, 2006), be useful as indicators of lithology, reservoir properties and the nature of fluid saturation in the specific area?; 2) Is it possible to reduce the risk in the exploration works for the Paleocene hydrocarbon accumulations and the discoveries in adjacent (Oligocene–Miocene) stratigraphic sections, where a few other prospects and structures have been identified?; 3) What is the probability of obtaining ambiguous results from the calculations, caused by the vertical and horizontal heterogeneity of the sediments.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

Similar in genesis and phase composition, to the hydrocarbon group, fields were found in the Bulgarian Black Sea shelf, on which the easternmost, deeply steeped part of the Moesian Platform, called the Varna monocline, lies. This is a broad transitional zone where a relatively weakly deformed platform sequence connects to the Western Black Sea Basin. This zone can be outlined where the relatively undeformed platform successions were downfaulted to the east during the mid-Cretaceous opening of the Western Black Sea Basin (Tari *et al.*, 1997). The main structural elements of the zone correspond to a folded Paleozoic base and relatively slightly deformed Mesozoic–Neozoic platform sedimentary sequence. The zone includes the eastern offshore part of the Varna and East Moesian monoclines (Fig. 1).

The western border of the Varna monocline, along the Paleozoic–Triassic structural succession, coincides with that of the Moesian Platform. To the north, it borders the southern slope of the Dobrudzha Massif, and to the south the Kamchiya Basin. To the east, the Varna monocline is limited by the Kaliakra (Western Black Sea) fault zone (Georgiev, 2012). Eastwards from the Varna monocline, the East Moesian monocline is located.

According to the Jurassic–Paleogene structural plan, the East Moesian monocline has a relatively simple structure (Bokov *et al.*, 2002). In the west-

ern part, closely east of the Kaliakra fault zone, the Tyulenovo-Elisavetino uplifted zone is formed. It is composed of meridionally to submeridionally trending near-fault structures (*i.e.*, East Krapets, North Shabla, Tyulenovo and Elisavetino), the western flanks of which moved down to several hundred meters. In its easternmost part, the monocline dips to the north, east, and south; towards the shelf edge, this dip is compensated by a gradual increase in the thickness of the Neogene–Quaternary sediments. The East Moesian monocline is characterized by a block structure, which is determined by faulting along two systems: northeastern and northwestern (Fig. 1). The first fault system is mainly extensional in nature. Typical representatives of this system are the Kaliakra-Razelm, and Venelin-Dobrich faults. The second, northwestern, fault system is older. In its evolution, processes of compression and displacement movements were observed. Of this type are the boundary faults Bliznatsi, in the south, and the Intra-Moesian (Silistra-Belgun) fault, in the north. The northern, marginal, part of the Moesian platform is located in the Romanian offshore. It includes heterogeneous elements that are affected to varying degrees by extension and destruction processes (Nikishin *et al.*, 2015).

The southern part of the Moesian Platform is a S–SE dipping carbonate plate, mainly composed of Jurassic and Cretaceous sediments overlain by thick “Tertiary” shale-marl-sandy deposits (Fig. 2). Its southern boundary is marked along the Bliznatsi fault zone, with an approximately W–E orientation, separating the platform area from the Kamchiya Basin. In the upraised, foot-wall block along the fault, and within the limits of the platform, a series of regional positive structures were marked on the Maastrichtian–Paleocene carbonate deposits (Galata, Kavarna, Kavarna East and Kaliakra), approximately following the direction of the fault and further complicated by several tectonic disturbances with a perpendicular direction.

The area around the Kaliakra fault zone, as an element of the offshore part of the Varna monocline and also of the western and the eastern parts of the Black Sea, has undergone significant transformations over time. Studies clarifying their nature, both regionally and locally, have been published from all neighboring Black Sea countries (*e.g.*, Tari *et al.*, 1997; Harbury and Cohen, 1997; Bokov *et al.*, 2002; Simmons *et al.*, 2018). Important for the geological history of the region is the thrusting of the Balkanides on the Moesian Platform during the Aptian–Albian rifting and the beginning of the back-arc rifting processes, as a result of the subduction of

the Paleotethys to the south. The significance of the event is reflected in the change of the sedimentary system and the increase in thickness of the deposits eastwards. During the Cenomanian, there was a

widespread transgression that continued until the Paleocene and extended along the southern edge of the platform. Carbonate sediments were deposited in the eastern and southeastern parts of the Moesian

Fig. 1. Tectonic scheme of the research area, according to Dabovski and Zagorchev (2009) and Georgiev (2012), with author's additions.

Fig. 2. Stratigraphic summary of the research area, according to Harbury and Cohen (1997), with author's modification.

Platform. Their lateral distribution was observed in the following offshore wells: Galata, Bogdanov East, Bogdanov North, Epsilon and Elisavetino. During the Maastrichtian, a high-energy shallow-marine environment prevailed at the southern end of the Moesian Platform. In this environment, the sediments of the Kaylaka Formation were deposited. At the end of the Paleocene, fine-carbonate and shallow-water massive bioclastic limestones (Komarevo and Kamen Del formations) were deposited. The latter are unconformably overlain by Eocene marls, which mark the subsidence of the platform caused by the thrusting of the Balkanides from the south. The Eocene marls are the main lithological variety that composes the Avren Formation. Several periods of extension, compression, faulting and inversion movements, along the NE–SW direction of the faults, followed during the Eocene and the Miocene. Most strongly, these events included the Kaliakra fault zone. As a result of a significant sea-level fall during the early–middle Eocene, the sedimentation was interrupted, leading to the formation of a regional unconformity. During the Oligocene, shale sedimentation prevailed. The glauconite sandstones, shales and argillaceous limestones (Ruslar Formation) are the main filling of the Kamchiya Basin and they hypsometrically align the basin with the Balkan thrust belt to the south and the Moesian platform to the north. According to Nikishin *et al.* (2015), the Black Sea was a freshwater basin with a fluvial setting of sedimentation during the Miocene. The sea was a subject to eustatic fluctuations, as a result of which the stratigraphic structure was complicated by numerous unconformities. River complexes formed during erosion periods, when sands were deposited.

Two predominant directions have been observed in the development of the main fault systems. The first one has an E–W trend. A typical representative is the Bliznatsi fault, which marks the southern boundary of the Moesian Platform. Its shape was greatly altered by Eocene–Oligocene erosion. It has been interpreted as extensional throughout its history. Extensional processes during the Eocene led to the formation of horst-like/near-fault structures located along the southern border of the Moesian Platform. The second direction of the main fault system has a NE–SW trend, and associates mainly with the Kaliakra Fault, but also with numerous smaller faults. During the Oligocene and the Miocene, the fault system was extensionally reactivated. In those times, numerous multidirectional and reversed changes occurred (*e.g.*, extensions, compressions, fracturing, transgressions, erosions), and

consequently, rocks of various, rapidly changing, both vertically and laterally, lithologies and petrophysical properties were deposited.

METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of this research, processed seismic data from the Bulgarian Black Sea shelf was used. In addition, all available information from a few wells (*e.g.*, logs, tests, and cores) was also used. The data were used for AVO and EEI seismic characterization analyses of the Paleocene and Oligocene–Miocene sedimentary successions. In order to obtain more accurate seismic reservoir characterization (also known as reservoir geophysics), the seismic, petrophysical and geological information (such as porosity and saturation) was integrated into the volumetric distribution of reservoir properties (see Shahri, 2013).

The different tools of the seismic reflection method provide vast amount of data that can help address the challenges and improve the interpretation of subsurface structures, as well as reveal more information about the properties of petroleum play elements and hydrocarbon prospects. Reflections occur at all layers in the subsurface where an appreciable change in acoustic impedance (AI) is observed by the propagating wave. It has been proved that a considerable amount of information is contained in seismic amplitude reflection, which can be related to porosity, lithology and even fluid change within the subsurface (Russell *et al.*, 2006). Although seismic amplitude is a fairly good indicator on the subsurface, several case studies have showed that it is an ambiguous indicator of hydrocarbon (*ibid.*). To overcome this limitation, AVO analysis was designed and developed as a commercial tool to examine the pre-stack seismic data for reservoir prediction and hydrocarbon indication in the petroleum industry. AVO response stems from a change in subsurface reflectivity as a function of the angle of incidence exhibited by seismic reflection events (Russell, 1999). A consequence of the increase in offset/angle is the reflectivity change. This reflectivity variation depends on the P- and S-wave velocity and density contrast over an interface. It has been proved that the change in fluid or lithology can give rise to variation in these properties, and thus varying AVO response (Russell *et al.*, 2006).

The principle is to take seismic data and process it to include all offsets of the data (full stack) or select offsets (partial stacks), particular set of offset range or incidence range. For the hydrocarbon anal-

ysis, it is often obtained a near-angle and a far-angle stack in addition to the full stack, and the events of near-angle to far-angle amplitude responses are compared. The difference in amplitude for a target interval on near versus far stacks can indicate the type of fluid within the pore space of a reservoir rock: brine, oil or gas. AVO analysis examines such amplitude differences. These procedures of AVO processing have been applied in the current research as well. When comparing the modeled responses for a near-offset with a far-offset trace, at both the top and the base of the reservoir, an increase in amplitude with offset or reflection angle was observed. The workflow started with the data conditioning of the well-logs and seismic data.

Seismic data conditioning was performed by applying trim statics and amplitude balance corrections before creating the synthetic seismogram in order to measure the correct amplitude variation with increasing the angle and offset. Tying well-logs to the seismic data at the correct location is an essential step for AVO analysis, as it is used to identify horizons to be picked for the initial model and for estimating the wavelet. Incorrect well-ties can lead to unreliable models, upon which the inversion is based, and thus reduce the confidence in the inverted volume. The first step of the well-tie procedure is the calibration of the sonic log and the check-shot, by matching the time-depth relationship from the integrated sonic log to the time-depth relationship from the check-shot study. The wavelet that gives an optimum tie of a well-log to a seismic section has characteristic phase, frequency, and amplitude. It is common to extract the seismic wavelet using statistical methods. Well-ties are done by using the Roy-White method, which utilizes a number of quality controls that are used to access the quality of the wavelet (White and Simm, 2003).

The next step of the methodology workflow is the deterministic simultaneous impedance inversion (Tonellot *et al.*, 2001), which is used to invert the pre-stack seismic data to P- and S-wave impedance (I_p and I_s) volumes and is adopted in this study. This is a model-based inversion, in which a global objective function is minimized to compute an optimal model for I_p and I_s , and for the density, which best explains all the angle stacks and the geologic knowledge introduced through an *a priori* low-frequency model (LFM) information of these properties. Input data was comprised of partial seismic angle stacks; extracted wavelets per angle stack; and I_p , I_s , and density LFMs. Synthetic seismograms were generated at the well locations, using the conditioned well-log data, to make well-ties for seismic to well-

log calibration and wavelet estimation for each angle stack.

The AVO analysis started with extracting common AVO attributes, including intercept (A) and gradient or slope (B), to be able to apply A/B (Two-term Aki-Richards), $A*B$ and $A+B$ for scaled Poisson's ratio change, to generate cross-plots and to identify and separate reservoir fluids and different lithological units. The AVO cross-plotting can be used to determine the AVO class and identify hydrocarbon-bearing sediments (Castagna and Swan, 1997). In general, five classes or types of AVO responses have been distinguished by the intercept and the slope or gradient (see Fig. 3):

- A Class 1 AVO response has a moderate to large positive amplitude value at the top of the reservoir at a zero-angle or offset. There is a significant decrease in amplitude with angle (decrease in positive numbers). For this class, the intercept is a moderate positive number and the slope is negative.
- Class 2 has a small negative amplitude value at the top of the reservoir at zero-angle or offset. There is a significant increase in amplitude with angle, which becomes more negative.
- A Class 2p AVO response has a small to moderate positive amplitude value at the top of the reservoir at zero-angle or offset. A significant increase in amplitude with angle is observed, which changes polarity from positive to negative values. Class 2 differs from Class 3 in that all the amplitudes are lower: the intercept is a small, rather than a moderate, negative number and the slope is negative for both and can have roughly the same value.
- Class 3 is the easiest to find and most reliable AVO response, which is characterized with a significant increase in negative amplitude with angle. On the amplitude versus angle plot, the amplitude at the top of the reservoir is negative at zero-angle (intercept) and becomes more negative as the angle increases (curves down – negative slope). In general, on the intercept versus gradient (slope) cross-plot, this is seen as a relatively high negative intercept and a negative gradient.
- Class 4 is theoretically possible, but is rare in nature. A Class 4 AVO response has a moderate to large negative amplitude value at the top of the reservoir at a zero-angle or offset. For this class, a significant decrease in negative amplitude with angle is observed. The intercept is a moderate negative number and the slope is positive.

Fig. 3. AVO Classes, according to (Castagna and Swan, 1997), with author's modification.

EEI was first introduced as a seismic attribute and method for fluid and lithology prediction by Whitcombe (2002). It is the application of angle rotation in the conventional acoustic impedance under certain approximation. EEI essentially works by projecting the intercept and gradient together with different angles, which highlights different features. It has the capability to estimate various elastic parameters, such as S-wave impedance, V_p/V_s , bulk modulus, shear modulus, Poisson's ratio and others. It also provides reservoir physical properties like porosity, clay content and water saturation. Its ability to predict fluids and lithology is well proven, especially where the acoustic impedance of gas-saturated sands and surrounding shale are almost equal. This approach allows a better distinction between the seismic anomaly caused by lithology and those caused by fluid content (hydrocarbon).

In this study, the concept of EEI inversion is used to derive the petrophysical properties and distribution of reservoir facies and establish a relationship between these attributes and well-log data.

Firstly, petrophysical analysis of the Paleocene and Oligocene–Miocene sedimentary successions was made. Rock physics of the formations were

examined to establish the relationship between the petrophysical data and the elastic properties. It involves the use of the well-logs to generate new log attributes, namely V_p/V_s , bulk modulus, shear modulus, Poisson's ratio, LMR (Lambda-Mu-Rho), etc. LMR expresses a relationship between the Lamé parameters λ (incompressibility), μ (rigidity) and ρ (density). It is followed by well-base cross-plot analysis for lithology and fluid determination, together with identification of the reservoir.

The initial step in the EEI method is to determine the best projection angle (χ) (called chi angle) for reservoir target parameters. Practically, in any EEI study, determining the optimum angle for particular target logs is the key to successful application of EEI and should be carefully evaluated. The final step consists of implementation and processing of EEI on seismic inversion data and interpretation of the outcomes of EEI inversion. This stage involves making new seismic inversion attributes for different petrophysical and elastic parameters (EEI seismic inversion attributes) to understand the key characteristic of the reservoir, which allows to distinguish different lithologies and fluid contents efficiently.

Fig. 4. Well-seismic tie for one of the wells.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, sufficient seismic data encompassing several wells located in the Bulgarian Black Sea shelf was used. The well-log data from some wells was also analyzed to evaluate the relationship between the elastic parameters, along with their potential for predicting lithology and fluid contents. Despite the limited number of wells available for wavelet estimation at well-ties, the preliminary wavelets demonstrated rather stable behavior (Fig. 4). Seismic data conditioning prior to the inversion tests encountered some problems with the alignment of the far and ultrafar offsets. Only the time alignment of the offset traces (trim statics) turned out to be challenging in some areas, especially around the Kaliakra fault due to residual moveout remaining in the gathers. Angle stacks analyzed in a number of well locations demonstrated good agreement with angle gathers.

For some of the wells, P- and S-wave velocity and density log were determined and used as main input to obtain petrophysical parameters and other attribute pairs required for rock physics study. In addition, the good-quality gamma ray (GR) and resistivity logs provide sufficient knowledge about location of the reservoir and improve log interpretation. The well-based cross-plot analysis of acoustic and elastic impedance parameters, used as a tool to establish quantitative relationship between reser-

voir properties, distinguishes different lithologies and fluid contents. Once the basic physical rock parameters were defined and analyzed, it became possible to generate other parameters that improve lithology and fluid discrimination.

Two types of inversion were tested. The first was simultaneous inversion, which requires LFM and delivers absolute impedance values. By that inversion, it became possible to calculate Poisson's ratio, λ - ρ , μ - ρ , V_p/V_s , etc. The second one applied in the study is EEI inversion, which does not require LFM, and therefore delivers only relative impedance values. At that inversion, lithology and fluid projections were calculated as optimum indicators.

Rock physics analysis based on AVO responses

Paleocene sedimentary succession

Taking into consideration the geological characteristics of the Paleocene reservoir from the gas fields in the study area, we found that the top reservoir response can generally be either a Class 1, which depicts shale on the reservoir, or Class 2, which describes harder, low porosity carbonate on the reservoir. Nevertheless, it would be difficult to understand from the AVO response whether the harder layer is present. In theory, if the harder layer is pre-

Fig. 5. AVO Class responses for structures in sediment succession with Oligocene Age.

sent, then the Class 1 response should be brighter due to an enhanced elastic contrast. The reservoir in one of the gas wells stands out as an anomaly, because it is softer than the overlying shale, in brine conditions, which produces a Class 2 AVO response. This is due to the fact that it has the highest porosity of all the reservoirs, and therefore the low value of V_p/ρ ratio. Hydrocarbon fill causes the Class 1 responses to dim, as the carbonate softens, reducing the contrast with the overlying shale, and the Class 2 responses to brighten, as the higher porosity carbonates become even softer than the overlying hard, low porosity carbonate.

Miocene–Oligocene sedimentary succession

One of the wells drilled a bright spot as if it was a gas accumulation, but in fact it turned out to be a very hard conglomerate. The AVO analysis showed that this is a strong Class 1 AVO anomaly, with a negative amplitude at zero offset that dims with the increase in offset. This would be indicative of a reservoir that is much harder than the overlying shale, when in fact the sand and shales are of similar hardness, although the sands are slightly harder. Gas will obviously soften the reservoir and the analysis shows that this should induce a polarity reversal, with gas sands showing a Class 2 AVO response, positive amplitude at zero offset that brightens with increasing offset. Therefore, bright spots that are

of Class 2 AVO are more likely to be hydrocarbon accumulations than bright spots that are of Class 1 AVO.

Actually, the AVO analysis and 2D modeling are focused on the Miocene–Oligocene sediments, where some structural locations and channel systems were studied (Fig. 5). The Oligocene channel generally shows a Class 1 AVO response for four locations studied, except a buildup of Class 2 AVO-like anomalies where a cluster or patchy up-dips was observed (Fig. 6). The first of the structures in the Middle Miocene sediments also showed a Class 1 AVO response, except for one interval in a down-dip location that showed a possible Class 2p response. The second prospect in that stratigraphic interval showed Classes 2 and 2p responses in an up-dip location. There is another one prospect in the Miocene sediments, which was also observed, and it showed a Class 1 AVO response. The examined Miocene channels are characterized by the lack of good quality near-offset data due to their shallow position. They consistently showed Class 2 AVO responses, which may be a result of background amplitude trend influence.

Rock physics analysis based on EEI inversion

At simultaneous inversion, the Poisson's ratio versus AI cross-plots is generated from wells and up-scaled seismically as well. When examining all the

Fig. 6. AVO Class responses for structures in sediment succession with Miocene Age.

Fig. 7. Poisson's ratio versus AI cross-plot, generated from: a) wells and b) upscaled seismic section.

Fig. 8. AI versus EEI cross plot at 38° degrees χ projection angle.

Fig. 9. EEI at angle of 38°, with gas wells and dry wells highlighted.

wells together, it was established that Poisson's ratio is the most promising fluid and lithology indicator, showing good separation between water and gas responses, although there is some overlap. When up-scaling the data to two-way time (tw_t), the same relationship holds for Poisson's ratio, but its use as a lithology discriminator is possibly lowered (Fig. 7). In general, the presence of gas in the reservoirs leads to low values of Poisson's ratio. A change in the ratio could potentially indicate a change in pore fluid and expressed in the AVO characteristics.

In this study, a projection of a χ angle of 38° through brine points gives a useful separation of brine, 10% gas and 90% gas reservoirs (Fig. 8). However, the amplitude of the resulting projection is still low, which may make it difficult to resolve fluid variation once seismic noise has been added. EEI (38°) optimizes fluid discrimination, but the magnitude of separation is considered weak. Rather limited separation between water and gas responses is obtained. Ambiguous response between gas field/gas wells and dry wells is observed (Fig. 9).

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions can be made:

- Our well-seismic ties shows a generally good match between seismic data and well data;
- Seismic data conditioning prior to the inversion tests encountered some problems with the alignment of the far and ultrafar offsets. The areas with this problem were limited and generally close to major faults (Kaliakra fault zone);
- Brine-filled reservoirs and conglomerates have a Class 1 AVO response, whereas gas-filled reservoirs show Class 2 AVO responses. In the Oligocene–Miocene sedimentary successions, Class 1, 2 and 2p AVO responses were identified.

REFERENCES

- Bokov, P., Doncheva, M., Kostova, N., Vakarelska, M., Tzenkova, V., Denkova, S. 2002. Structure and hydrocarbon potential of the deepwater part of the Bulgarian Black Sea economic zone. *Geology and Mineral resources* 6, 18–22 (in Bulgarian).
- Castagna, J.P., Swan, H.W. 1997. Principles of AVO cross-plotting. *The Leading Edge* 16 (4), 337–344, <https://doi.org/10.1190/1.1437626>.
- Dabovski, H., Zagorchev, I. 2009. Alpine tectonic subdivision of Bulgaria. In: Zagorchev, I., Dabovski, H., Nikolov, T.

- Poisson's ratio was identified to be the most promising attribute for fluid identification that could be calculated with a simultaneous inversion;
- EEI 38 was identified as the best angle projection to discriminate fluids using EEI inversion, although the separation between water and gas responses was somewhat limited;
- Inversion tests were run focusing on the Maastrichtian–Paleocene sedimentary successions for a large part of the studied area, including all of the existing fields, and the result shows that EEI 38 provided the higher signal to noise ratio of the two inversion types. Despite EEI 38 showing better overall results compared to simultaneous inversion, neither one managed to provide good differentiation of water and gas responses;
- Both inversion types showed similar responses between some of the gas fields and structural lows, which could be an indication of a strong lithological footprint (porosity) on the different fluid discriminators;
- None of the currently identified prospects in the Maastrichtian–Paleocene interval have a distinctive signature with respect to their immediate background that could indicate hydrocarbon accumulations.

In general, it should be noted that geophysical de-risking of the existing prospect in the Maastrichtian–Paleocene interval has proved to be challenging. For more detailed reservoir characterization, additional geological and geophysical studies are required. In this regard, the obtained parameters of the studied sedimentary successions should be evaluated qualitatively, but not quantitatively.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the reviewers Prof. Gotse Tenchov (National Institute of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography) and Assoc. Prof. Reneta Raykova (Sofia University), for their corrections that helped to improve the quality of the manuscript.

- (Eds), *Geology of Bulgaria. Volume II, Mesozoic Geology*. Sofia, "Prof. Marin Drinov" Academic Publishing House, 30–37 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Georgiev, G. 2012. Geology and hydrocarbon systems in the Western Black Sea. *Turkish Journal of Earth Sciences* 21 (5), 723–754, <https://doi.org/10.3906/yer-1102-4>.
- Harbury, N., Cohen, M. 1997. Sedimentary history of the Late Jurassic – Paleogene of Northeast Bulgaria and the Bulgarian Black Sea. In: Robinson, A.G. (Ed.), *Regional and Petroleum Geology of the Black Sea and Surrounding Region: AAPG Memoir* 68, 129–168, <https://doi.org/10.1306/M68612C9>.
- Hicks, G., Francis, A. 2006. Extended Elastic impedance and its relation to AVO crossplotting and V_p/V_s . *68th Annual International Conference and Exhibition, EAGE, Extended Abstracts*, P056, <https://doi.org/10.3997/2214-4609.201402386>.
- Nikishin A.M., Okay, A.I., Tüysüz, O., Demirer, A., Amelin, N., Petrov, E. 2015. The Black Sea basins structure and history: New model based on new deep penetration regional seismic data. Part 1: Basins structure and fill. *Marine and Petroleum Geology* 59, 638–655, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpetgeo.2014.08.017>.
- Russell, B. 1999. AVO adds flavor to seismic soup. *AAPG Explorer* 18 (5), 112–117.
- Russell, B., Hampson, D., Bankhead, B. 2006. An inversion primer. *CSEG RECORDER* 31 (2), 96–103.
- Simmons, M.D., Tari, G.C., Okay, A.I. 2018. Petroleum Geology of the Black Sea: Introduction. In: Simmons, M.D., Tari, G.C., Okay, A.I. (Eds), *Petroleum Geology of the Black Sea*. Geological Society, London, Special Publications, 464, 1–18, <https://doi.org/10.1144/SP464.15>.
- Shahri, S. 2013. *Application of extended elastic impedance (EEI) to improve reservoir characterization*. PhD thesis, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, 96 pp.
- Tari, G., Dicea, O., Faulkerson, J., Georgiev, G., Popov, S., Stefanescu, M., Weir, G. 1997. Cimmerian and Alpine stratigraphy and structural evolution of the Moesian Platform (Romania/Bulgaria). In: Robinson, A.G. (Ed.), *Regional and petroleum geology of the Black Sea and surrounding region*. AAPG Memoir 68, 63–90, <https://doi.org/10.1306/M68612C6>.
- Tonellot, T., Macé, D., Richard, V. 2001. Joint stratigraphic inversion of angle limited stacks: *71st Annual International Meeting, SEG, Expanded Abstracts*, 227–230, <https://doi.org/10.1190/1.1816577>.
- Whitcombe, D.N., Connolly, P.A., Reagan, R.L., Redshaw, T.C. 2002. Extended elastic impedance for fluid and lithology prediction. *Geophysics* 67 (1), 63–67, <https://doi.org/10.1190/1.1451337>.
- White, R., Simm, R. 2003. *Tutorial – Good Practice in Well Ties*. *First Break* 21 (10), 27 pp., <https://doi.org/10.3997/1365-2397.21.10.25640>.